

NEWSLETTER # 2

FARMWISE PROJECT

2025

The project involves 17 beneficiaries and 3 associated partners from 13 countries. This multi-disciplinary project, funded by the EU research and innovation program **Horizon Europe (GAP-101135533)**, brings together experts in water management, agriculture, climate, sensors, earth observation, data and AI, aiming to develop sustainable solutions to address sustainable water management, and climate change challenges.

Revolutionising Water Management & Agriculture in Europe

**COLLABORATIVE
SOLUTIONS FOR
SUSTAINABLE
FARMING**

What this Newsletter covers

- **How FARMWISE Unites Data, People and Farms: Watch our new short video**
- **University of East Anglia-FARMWISE team Showcases Agri-Tech Innovation at the Royal Norfolk Show**
- **FARMWISE Futures Session Unites Stakeholders at MACFRUT 2025 to Tackle Climate and Water Challenges**
- **How can the EU's Eastern Partner Countries strengthen investment in water security?**

We're pleased to share the latest developments from our Horizon Europe-funded project, which focuses on advancing sustainable farming through innovative technologies and artificial intelligence (AI).

Spanning eight case studies, our work is already making a meaningful impact on water management and agricultural productivity across Europe.

In this newsletter, we highlight key updates on our progress and a closer look at how we're driving innovation to shape the future of sustainable agriculture.

Introduction to the FARMWISE Project

- **Project** 101135533 – FARMWISE
- **Type of Action:** HORIZON-RIA
- **Cluster 6:** "Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment"
- **Topic:** HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-1 - Knowledge and innovative solutions in agriculture for water availability and quality
- **Duration:** 36 months **Start date:** 01.01.2024

FARMWISE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101135533.

HOW FARMWISE UNITES DATA, PEOPLE AND FARMS - NEW VIDEO

New 4-minute film launched! Find out how FARMWISE is turning knowledge into action

Can European agriculture feed a growing population and protect our water, soil, and ecosystems? FARMWISE says ‘yes’ – by connecting data, people, and innovation to create real-world solutions for sustainable farming.

Discover how:

- ✓ Farmers, scientists, and policymakers collaborate across 8 pilot regions
- ✓ COSMIC and VDSS digital tools drive smarter water management
- ✓ 11 innovations are tested directly on farms
- ✓ Climate models are helping Europe prepare for droughts and floods
- ✓ FARMWISE is building lasting skills and networks to support future generations

[Watch the video here](#)

[Learn more on our website](#)

University of East Anglia–FARMWISE team Showcases Agri-Tech Innovation at the Royal Norfolk Show

The University of East Anglia–FARMWISE team participated across both days of the Royal Norfolk Show (25–26 June 2025), hosted in the Agri-TechE Innovation Hub (Stand 333) at the Norfolk Showground. Team members Kevin Hiscock, Andrew Lovett, Richard Cooper, and Natasha Balashova engaged with visitors to highlight the project's innovative contributions to sustainable farming and water management.

Throughout both days, UEA researchers showcased the next generation of precision agriculture and AI including a live AmoreAqua dashboard demo, allowing visitors to explore real-time stream flow and water quality data from the Defra-funded Wensum Demonstration Catchment, highlighting applications that empower farmers with interactive, data-driven decision support.

[Read the full article on our website](#)

FARMWISE Futures Session Unites Stakeholders at MACFRUT 2025 to Tackle Climate and Water Challenges

FARMWISE launched its first national foresight session on 6 May 2025 at MACFRUT, Italy's leading international agriculture fair. Hosted in the "Acqua Campus – The Water Revolution" area, the session addressed how agricultural stakeholders can jointly respond to increasing climate and water-related pressures.

Led by Canale Emiliano Romagnolo (CER), owner and coordinator of the Italian case study, and supported by the FARMWISE team in Valencia, the session drew strong participation from institutions, agro-industries, cooperatives, farmers and academic actors—including CER, Ferrero HCO, COPROB-Italia Zuccheri, Orogel, Mutti and the University of Bologna (UNIBO).

Using Mentimeter, participants ranked future climate risks such as drought, flooding, and declining soil fertility, followed by an open roundtable exploring how technology and supply chain agreements can boost resilience.

“This session brought together vision, data, and grounded experience. We're facing urgent challenges, but also strong collaboration potential,” said Nicola Dalmonte – Chairperson of CER.

Further insights included:

- Italia Zuccheri's experiences with climate stress on key crops like sugar beet
- The Emilia-Romagna region's €70 million funding for horticulture and supply chain resilience
- The strategic value of supply chain agreements for price stability, innovation investment, and access to national/EU funding
- Calls for integrated approaches to water reuse, leak prevention, and digital irrigation networks

The session concluded with an on-site demo by UNIBO and CER, showcasing biosensors, nutrient monitoring, and AI-powered water management systems.

FARMWISE will replicate this format across other European case studies to develop a comprehensive roadmap for climate-resilient and water-smart agriculture.

IN OTHER NEWS:

How can the EU's Eastern Partner Countries strengthen investment in water security?

A new paper applies the OECD Scorecard to assess investment conditions for water security in the EU's Eastern Partner Countries – Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine. Conducted under the EU4Environment – Water Resources and Environmental Data Programme, it highlights key challenges, progress to date and policy actions to attract sustainable water security investments.

Policy recommendations include:

- ✓ Leveraging EU accession experiences from countries with similar reform paths
- ✓ Developing coherent national strategies and investment plans for the water sectors in Eastern Partner Countries
- ✓ Strengthening enforcement of economic and regulatory instruments to improve cost recovery and water quality
- ✓ Exploring diversified financing, including climate funds and nature-based solutions
- ✓ Reducing non-revenue water – water that enters the distribution system, but is not billed to customers – to improve the financial sustainability of utilities and strengthen the investment case

Find out more → https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/assessing-the-enabling-environment-for-investment-in-water-security-in-the-eu-s-eastern-partner-countries_3f5d9a13-en.html

PROJECT OVERVIEW

FARMWISE aims to develop **AI-based tools to enhance European water policy and decision-making** through precise data analytics and interactive visualisation & research-driven technologies for water resource management in agricultural landscapes, **ensuring resilience against climate change and promoting environmental sustainability.**

Our project harnesses **the power of 11 cutting-edge technologies to revolutionise agriculture and water management** in various European regions. These technologies are designed to empower farmers with choices to maximise their productivity, optimise resource usage, and promote sustainability.

SPANNING THREE YEARS FROM JANUARY 2024 UNTIL DECEMBER 2026, FARMWISE'S GOALS ARE TO:

- Develop improved tools based on AI for efficient European water policy and decision-making.
- Utilise an integrated systems thinking approach to enhance sustainable water management.
- Establish comprehensive European-scale databases on water quantity, quality, and availability.
- Assess the efficacy and scalability of innovative solutions through advanced field tests.
- Develop and implement integrated strategies for agricultural risk assessment and mitigation.
- Create an interactive decision support system for improved agriculture management using AI and Machine Learning (ML)

CASE STUDIES AND DEMONSTRATORS:

Location & Operator

Eight case studies across Europe will test and evaluate the impact of the innovations in diverse agricultural and climatic contexts.

The project will serve as a testing ground for sustainable value chains. *Locations of the case studies are the Netherlands, Poland, the UK, Spain, Italy, Ukraine, Finland and Sweden.*

PARTNERS

The FARMWISE consortium includes 17 beneficiaries and 3 associated partners from 13 countries.

Visit our website
Watch our new video
Find out the latest!

farmwise-project.eu

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